

Resistance of IR varieties to race 1 (PXO86) and race 2 (PXO61) of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*. Index based on resistance of IR24 0-9 d after inoculation. + = more resistance than IR24, - = more susceptible than IR24.

Three races — PXO86, PXO79, PXO99—virulent on cultivars carrying *Xa-4*, and 3 avirulent races—PXO61, PXO112, and PXO71—were used to inoculate plants at 20, 40, and 60 d after sowing (DAS). IR24, which is not known to carry *Xa-4*, was the susceptible check.

Lesion areas were estimated at 9, 15, and 23 d after inoculation (DAI) and converted to a relative resistance index (RI) based on the lesion area of IR24. (The estimation of RI based on lesion area was similar to that based on hill or leaf infection.) Here, RI is an indication of lesion expansion across time after initial infection.

The IR cultivars showed high relative resistance to the three avirulent races (see table). To the virulent races that matched gene *Xa-4*, relative resistance was low. In all cases, the virulence × resistance index interaction was not significant, apparently indicating that background resistance does not interact with race.

RI for PXO61, avirulent to *Xa-4* and PXO86, virulent, were compared to determine the effect of *Xa-4* and the

corresponding background resistance on selected IR cultivars. By 20 DAS, *Xa-4* had shown its effect, as indicated by high RI to PXO61 (see figure).

Background resistance was indicated by RI unmatched by PXO86. At 40 and 60 DAS, lesions ceased to expand. RI values decreased because of the susceptible check cultivar.

Lesion expansion may be a better parameter to detect the effect of both *Xa-4* and background resistance at an early stage. Such measurements may

provide an accurate assessment of background resistance, as the variance seems to be small. The data also indicate that lesion expansion varies among cultivars.

Our studies also indicate that IR24 may not be the most appropriate susceptible check. If a more susceptible cultivar were used, the difference might be more evident and the background resistance more accurately distinguished. □

Insect resistance

ACM18 (IET7804), a high-yielding gall midge (GM)-resistant rice

S. Sevugaperumal, G. Logiswaran, S. Jebaraj, G. Soundrapandian, and P. C. Sundara Babu, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai 625104, Tamil Nadu, India

We evaluated 13 rice cultivars against susceptible and resistant checks for yield potential and reaction to GM in the field. The experiment was in unprotected conditions with 2 replications in 4.8-m² plots. Seedlings

were transplanted at 28 d on 20 Oct 1986, late in the season to capture a high pest population buildup. Susceptible IR20 was planted around the experimental plots to ensure adequate pest pressure.

Damage by GM was estimated as percentage of plants affected and % silvershoots at 50 d after transplanting (DT) and graded according to the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) scale. Days to 50% flowering and yield were also recorded.

ACM18 (IET7804), a cross derivative of OR158-5/Rasi, had the lowest GM incidence (2.23%), followed by IET9690, Surekha, and IET9688 (Table 1). ACM18 had the highest grain yield (5.3 t/ha in 120 d), 32.5% more than that of IR20 and 10 d earlier.

Table 1. Reaction to GM and yield of 15 rices. Tamil Nadu, India, 1986.

Culture	50 DT ^a			Days to 50% flowering	Grain yield (t/ha)	% of IR20
	Plants damaged (%)	Silvershoots (%)	Infestation score ^b			
ACM18 (IET7804)	0.33 (0.88)	2.23 (1.37)	3	90	5.3	132.5
IET8629	4.50 (2.23)	11.10 (3.39)	5	75	4.6	115.0
IET8633	1.90 (1.52)	11.56 (3.48)	5	75	3.8	95.0
IET8803	9.60 (3.10)	10.56 (3.32)	5	77	3.6	90.0
IET9234	8.66 (3.01)	10.93 (3.38)	5	100	3.1	77.5
IET9247	2.40 (1.67)	9.03 (3.07)	5	95	2.5	62.5
IET9587	3.50 (1.98)	10.93 (3.36)	5	85	5.1	127.5
IET9688	0.30 (0.87)	4.76 (1.76)	3	99	2.9	72.5
IET9689	1.50 (1.41)	10.30 (3.26)	5	82	4.9	122.5
IET9690	0.60 (0.98)	2.76 (1.46)	3	76	4.6	115.0
IET9692	4.63 (2.26)	10.83 (3.36)	5	89	4.1	102.5
IET9695	3.00 (1.85)	9.16 (3.09)	5	100	1.3	32.5
IET9699	3.30 (1.94)	10.33 (3.24)	5	74	4.4	110.0
Surekha (resistant check)	0.60 (1.02)	4.03 (1.94)	3	90	5.1	127.5
IR20 (susceptible check)	11.86 (3.51)	12.56 (3.62)	5	100	4.0	100.0
LSD (0.05)	(0.65)	(1.15)	—	—	0.9	—

^a Figures in parentheses are transformed values. ^b By SES.

Table 2. Results of artificially inoculating rices with GM. Tamil Nadu, India, 1986.

Rice	Tillers (no./hill)	GM-affected tillers (no./hill)	Affected tillers (%)	Infestation score
ACM18 (IET7804)	15	0	0.0	0
IET9688	17	3	17.6	7
IET9690	12	2	16.7	7
IR20 (susceptible check)	14	6	42.9	7
Surekha (resistant check)	13	1	7.7	5

The same three rices were tested under artificial conditions. Five unemerged galls were introduced into each caged plant. After 25 d, percentage of affected tillers was 7.7 in resistant check Surekha, 42.9 in susceptible check IR20, and 0 in ACM18 (Table 2). □

Screening rice varieties with different growth durations for spider mite *Oligonychus oryzae* infestation

A. Prakash, J. Rao, and D. C. Asthana, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack 7.53006, India

Sixteen rice varieties with short, medium, and long growth durations were transplanted in 4- × 4-m plots in the field during 1986 wet season. An aqueous suspension of spider mite *O. oryzae* containing 100 adults/250 ml water was sprayed on rice foliage 10 d after transplanting.

Severe mite infestation 40 d after spraying caused yellowing. Mite populations (eggs, juveniles, and adults) were recorded from a 10 cm² leaf area on 10 hills/plot chosen at random.

No test variety was free from mite infestation (see table). The mite population was highest in long-duration

Spider mite populations in rice varieties of different growth durations. Cuttack, India, 1986 wet season.

Variety	Parents	Duration ^a (d)	Mites ^b (no./10 cm ²)
Subhadra	TNI/SR26-13	90 S	18.9 a
Bala	N22/TN1	105 S	20.4 a
Kalinga-II	AC540/Ratna	80 S	28.2 b
Vani	IR8/CR1014	125 M	28.9 b
Parijat	TKM6/TN1	115 M	30.0 b
Kesari	Kumar/Jagannath	95 S	30.6 b
Sattari	Mut-Sel (NSJ200/Padma)	70 S	32.6 b
Pankaj	Peta/Tonkai Rotan	145 L	34.0 b
Savitri	Pankaj/Jagannath	155 L	39.6 c
Utkal Prabha	Waikoku/CR1014	155 L	40.5 c
Karuna	IR8/Adt 27	125 M	47.8 d
Jaya	T141/TN1	130 M	50.8 d
Jagannath	T141 mutant	150 L	53.4 d
Ratna	TKM6/IR8	125 M	60.2 e
Vijaya	T90/IR8	140 L	62.8 e
CR1018	Culture	155 L	70.5 f

^aS = short duration, M = medium duration, L = long duration. ^bMean of 3 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

CR1018 and lowest in short-duration Subhadra. Within the same duration group, some varieties showed significantly different populations.

Population differences were not significant between all varieties of one duration and all varieties of another duration. □

Leafhopper (LF) epidemic in Haryana

K. S. Kushwaha, Haryana Agricultural University (HAU), Rice Research Station (RRS), Kaul (Kurukshetra), Haryana, India

Rice LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* historically has occurred only as a sporadic and minor rice pest. But during the 1987 wet season (kharif), it struck in an epidemic intensity. Karnal, Kurukshetra, Ambala, and Sirsa districts were badly damaged.

Infestation started the first week of Aug and lasted to the first week of Oct. Peak infestation was during the second week

LF damage on rice in Haryana, India, 1987.

Variety	Tillers/hill ^a			Leaves/hill ^b			Length/leaf			Larvae (no./10 leaves)
	No.	Affected	%	No.	Folded	%	Length (cm)	Length affected (cm)	%	
Jaya	8.3	5.8	70	44.2 (6.72)	30.5 (5.31)	47	46.4	9.4	20	12.2
HKR120	10.3	10.1	98	51.7 (7.14)	51.5 (7.22)	100	37.2	19.0	50	18.2
PR106	8.9	8.6	97	44.5 (6.74)	42.8 (6.62)	96	42.4	24.6	58	13.5
IET8113	9.7	8.6	89	48.4 (6.96)	36.1 (6.00)	78	40.6	19.1	78	14.7
IET8116	12.3	11.0	98	51.2 (7.21)	36.2 (6.01)	85	39.6	15.6	62	15.7
Pakistan Basmati	14.4	14.4	100	67.2 (8.26)	66.0 (8.19)	100	71.9	60.6	84	52.0
LSD (0.05)	2.8	4.0		(0.60)	(1.75)		9.3	4.7		4.7

^aAv of 20 hills. ^bAv of 20 leaves. Figures in parentheses are $\sqrt{n+1}$ values.

of Sep, when the rice crop was at the booting to panicle emergence stage. No variety was untouched, but varieties

with relatively broader leaves had less infestation. The pest caused 30-80% yield loss.